

A Study on Mechanical Properties of Self-compacting Concrete using Fly Ash and Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS)

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Abstract-

Self-compacting concrete (SCC) has gained significant attention in recent years due to its ability to flow and fill formwork without the need for vibration, thus enhancing construction efficiency. This study investigates the mechanical properties of SCC incorporating fly ash (FA) and ground granulated blast furnace slag (GGBS) as partial replacements for cement. The experimental program encompasses a comprehensive evaluation of fresh properties, including workability and flowability, as well as hardened properties such as compressive strength, tensile strength, and flexural strength. Mixtures with varying proportions of FA and GGBS are investigated to assess their influence on the performance of SCC. The results indicate that the incorporation of FA and GGBS positively impacts the workability and mechanical strength of SCC, leading to sustainable and durable concrete structures. This research contributes valuable insights into the optimization of SCC formulations with supplementary cementitious materials, offering potential benefits for both construction industry practices and environmental sustainability.

Keywords:

Self-compacting concrete, Fly ash, Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag, Fresh and Hardened properties.

I. INTRODUCTION

The self-compacting or very good workable concrete, also referred to as self – consolidating concrete is a highly flow able or self levelling cohesive concrete that can spread willingly into place (low thickness) through and around thick reinforcement under its own weight. It sufficiently

fills form work without segregation or bleeding, and without the need for major vibration. SCC mix has a low yield stress and an increased flexibility thickness. The mix require minimum force to initial flow yet have sufficient cohesion to oppose aggregate segregation and extreme bleeding., coarse aggregate can float in the mortar without segregate. The yield stress is condensed by using a highly developed synthetic high range water-reducing admixture (HRWR), while the viscosity of paste is improved by using a viscosity modify admixture (VMA) or by rising the percentage of fines integrated into the Self Compacting Concrete mix design.

Self-compacting concrete (SCC) also referred to as “self-consolidating concrete,” has newly been one of the most important developments in the construction industry. SCC, require no compaction energy and use of vibrators inside entirely filling the formwork yet in the attendance of dense reinforcement has been developed in Japan in the late 1980s, to improve the reliability of concrete and concrete structures. In order to achieve this property, SCC must have good deformability, high segregation resistance, and no blocking around reinforcements without applying any vibration.

New generation of admixtures added to fresh SCC to increase cohesion and segregation resistance. Good segregation resistance means that the distributions of aggregate particles in the concrete are relatively equivalent at all locations and at all levels. The hardened SCC is dense, homogeneous, and has better engineering and mechanical properties than traditional vibrated concrete. Though, to design a proper Self Compacting Concrete mixture is not a easy chore. A key part, when produce Self Compacting Concrete, defamation on the selection of ingredient materials and the design of mix proportions so as to get sufficient properties of freshly concrete.

Typically, SCC uses less volume of coarse aggregates, less w/c ratio, and employs super plasticizers. The use of super plasticizers generates extremely deformable SCC. The low volume of coarse aggregates come at the expenditure of improved volume of cement powder, most important to high temperature production problems and higher expenses in addition to the improved total shrinkage. In this study, the cement powder in SCC is moderately replaced with supplementary cementitious materials. Typically; these admixtures contain Fly Ash (FA), and Ground Granulated Blast-furnace Slag (GGBS).

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Okamura [1] studied both a rational mix design method and an appropriate acceptance testing method at the job site are close to being established for self- compacting concrete, it is considered that the main obstacles to the wide use of self- compacting concrete have been removed.

The next task is to distribute the techniques for manufacturing and construction of self-compacting concrete rapidly. Rational training and qualification systems for engineers should be introduced. In addition, new structural design and construction systems making full use of the benefits of self-compacting concrete should be introduced. Once self-compacting concrete becomes so widely used that it is seen as a 'standard concrete' rather than as a 'special concrete', we will have succeeded in creating durable and reliable concrete structures requiring precise maintenance work.

Bartle Person [2] approved out an investigational and numerical study on mechanical properties, such as strength, elastic modulus, creep and shrinkage of self-compacting concrete and the correspondence properties of normal compacting concrete. The revised incorporated mix proportions of preserved or air-cured sampling with water binder ratio (w/b) varying between 0.24 and 0.80. Fifty percent of the mixes are self-compacting concrete and period was normal compacting concrete. The age at load of the concretes in the creep study various between 2 and 90 days. Strength and relative wetness were also originated. The results indicate that elastic modulus, creep and shrinkage of SCC do not differ significantly from the equal properties of Normal Concrete.

Masahiro Ouchi et al. [3] address the two major issues faced by the international community in using SCC, namely the absence of a proper mix design method and jivial testing method. They proposed a mix design method for SCC based on paste and mortar studies for super plasticizer compatibility followed by trail mixes. However, it was emphasized that the need to test the final product for passing ability, filling ability, and flow ability and segregation resistance was more relevant.

Nan Su et al. [4] planned a new mix design method for self-compacting concrete. First, the amount of aggregates necessary was resolute, and the paste of binder was then full into the voids of aggregates to make certain that the concrete thus obtain has flow ability, self-compacting ability and other required SCC properties. The amount of aggregates, binders and mixing water, as well as type and amount of super plasticizer to be used are the main factors influence the properties of SCC. Slump flow, V-funnel, L-flow, U-box and compressive strength tests were approved out to observe the act of SCC, and the results indicate that the anticipated method could be used to make effectively SCC of high quality. Compared to the method urbanized by the Japanese Ready-Mixed Concrete Association (JRMCA), this method is simpler, easier for performance and less sustained, requires a smaller quantity of binders and saves cost.

Felekoglu et al. [5] has done research on effect of w/c ratio on the fresh and hardened properties of SCC. According to the author adjustment of w/c ratio and super plasticizer dosage is one of the key properties in proportioning of SCC mixtures. In this research, fine mixtures with different combinations of w/c ratio and super plasticizer dosage levels were investigated. The

results of this research show that the optimum w/c ratio for producing SCC is in the range of 0.84-1.07 by volume. The ratio above and below this range may cause blocking or segregation of the mixture.

Afat Siddique [6] carried Slump flow, L-box and U-box values decrease with increase in iron slag whereas there is increase in V-funnel time. Workability of SCC mixtures decreases due to increase of iron slag percentage cause may be multi-angle and rough in surface of iron slag aggregates. Increases friction between particles may responsible for the results. Compressive strength of SCC mixes increase with iron slag content, and also with age. At 28 days, strength increases by 21% over control SCC.

III. METHODOLOGY

The proposed methodology is followed to fabricating the GGBS Self-compacting mixes with different industrial wastes.

Fig.1 Flow chart of the current study.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results and discussion chapter explains the mechanical strength properties like

compressive strength, split tensile strength, flexural strength, non-destructive test (rebound hammer) and young's modulus test of concrete mixture with fly ash and ground granulated blast furnace slag. Below table provides the details of mix designation of the composites.

Table.1. Mix designations of the concrete mixes.

Mix Designation	Proportions of Binding Materials
A1	100% cement
A2	90% cement + 10% fly ash
A3	85% cement + 10% fly ash + 5% GGBS
A4	80% cement + 10% fly ash + 10% GGBS

FRESH PROPERTIES:

Fig.2 (a) Slump flow result in mm, (b). Slump flow result in sec, (c). V-funnel, (d). L-Box results.

The slump flow values ranged from 630 mm to 680 mm, indicating varying degrees of flowability. Mix A1 had the highest slump flow at 680 mm, suggesting it had the greatest flowability, while mix A2 had the lowest at 630 mm. The slump flow time (T50cm) values ranged from 5 seconds to 9 seconds. A lower T50cm value indicates a quicker spread of the mix. Mix A2, with a T50cm of 5 seconds, demonstrated the fastest flow, while mix A1 had the slowest flow, taking 9

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The V-funnel test measures the flow rate of the concrete mix, with lower times indicating better flowability. Mixes A1 and A3 had the shortest V-funnel times at 9 seconds, indicating they had the best flow properties among the tested mixes. Mix A2 had the longest V-funnel time at 12 seconds, reflecting poorer flowability. Mix A4 showed moderate flowability with a V-funnel time of 10 seconds.

The L-box test assesses the passing ability of the concrete, with a higher ratio indicating better passing ability through reinforcement without segregation. Mix A1 achieved the highest L-box ratio of 0.87, suggesting superior passing ability. Mix A3 followed closely with a ratio of 0.85. Mixes A4 and A2 had the lowest ratios, 0.83 and 0.81 respectively, indicating relatively poorer passing abilities.

HARDENED PROPERTIES OF SCC:

(a). Compressive Strength

Fig.3 (a) Compressive Strength (b). Split tensile Strengths of GGBS Concrete mixes.

The compressive strengths of GGBS concrete mixes showed a consistent increase in strength from 7 to 28 days. Mix A1 had the highest increase in compressive strength over time, suggesting a robust mix design with effective use of Fly Ash and GGBS. Mix A3, while initially lower than A1, demonstrated a comparable strength gain by 28 days. Mixes A2 and A4, although lower in strength, exhibited steady strength development, indicating their suitability for applications where moderate strength is sufficient.

(b). Split Tensile Strengths

The Split tensile strengths of GGBS concrete mixes showed a consistent increase in split tensile strength from 7 to 28 days. Mix A1 had the highest increase in strength over time, indicating a strong mix design with effective use of Fly Ash and GGBS. Mix A3 also showed substantial strength development, second only to A1. Mixes A2 and A4, while exhibiting lower overall strengths, displayed steady strength growth, suitable for applications requiring moderate tensile strength.

(c). Flexural Strength

The flexural strength of four SCC mixes (A1, A2, A3, and A4) was evaluated at 28 days to understand the impact of Fly Ash and GGBS on the flexural performance of the concrete. Mix A4 had the highest flexural strength at 6.35 MPa, indicating superior performance under bending stress. Mix A1 closely followed with a flexural strength of 6.16 MPa, showing excellent performance as well. Mix A3 exhibited a flexural strength of 6.06 MPa, also demonstrating strong performance. Mix A2 had the lowest flexural strength at 4.74 MPa, indicating it is less capable of withstanding bending stresses compared to the other mixes.

(D). Young’s Modulus test results

The young’s Modulus test strength results for various replacement levels of fly ash and GGBS by Cement such as normal concrete and 0%, 5%, 10% percentages of SCC consider at 28-days strength. The young’s modulus of the A4 mix showed improved properties compared to pristine, A2 and A3 mixes.

1. CONCLUSION

Based on the comprehensive analysis of the fresh and hardened properties of self- compacting concrete (SCC) with various proportions of Fly Ash and Ground Granulated Blast Furnace Slag (GGBS), several conclusions can be drawn:

- The fresh properties of Mix A1 (100% cement) exhibited slump flow of 680mm and longest T50cm (9 sec), Mix A2 (90% cement + 10% fly ash) 630 mm and fastest T50cm (5 sec) and Mix A3 (85% cement + 10% fly ash + 5% GGBS) and Mix A4 (80% cement + 10% fly ash + 10% GGBS) had intermediate slump flows and T50cm values, suggesting balanced flowability and spread times.
- Mix A1 consistently exhibited the highest strengths and best fresh properties, making it suitable for applications requiring high performance, both in terms of workability and mechanical properties.
- Mix A3 demonstrated a good balance of fresh and hardened properties, showing that partial replacement of cement with Fly Ash and GGBS can enhance both flowability and strength, making it a viable option for sustainable construction.
- Mix A4, with higher GGBS content, showed good flexural strength and moderate compressive and tensile strengths, indicating its suitability for specific structural applications where bending resistance is crucial.
- Mix A2 had the lowest strengths and poorer flow properties, suggesting that a 10% replacement of cement with Fly Ash alone may not be optimal for high-strength applications but could be considered for less critical structures where cost and sustainability are prioritized.

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